

THE IMPACT OF MENTAL DISORDERS ON CHILDREN'S HEALTH

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ABSTRACT

There are many uncertainties about the origin of mental illness. There are many causes for mental illness. The origin, development, course and outcome of mental illness depend on the interaction of various harmful effects of the environment, external (exogenous) and internal (endogenous) factors

Some diseases that occur in children lead to mental disorders in children, especially endogenous factors include heredity, state of nervous activity, constitutional and pre-disease characteristics of the person, sex, age, immunological and reactive state of the organism.

Exogenous factors include infections (influenza, chronic tonsillitis, rheumatism, brucellosis, sweating, trauma, AIDS, encephalitis, meningoencephalitis, etc.), intoxications (alcoholism, drugs, drugs, industrial and agricultural poisons), brain injuries, acute or chronic diseases of the body (cardiovascular, pulmonary, gastric, digestive tract diseases), disorders of endogenous glands (thyroid, pancreas, adrenal glands, etc.), diseases of the cerebral vessels (cerebral arteriosclerosis, coronary heart disease), brain tumors and

parasites (echinococcus, cysticercosis, mental injuries, etc.).

In psychiatry, as in other fields, there are many unexplored issues between cause and effect. The importance of endogenous and exogenous etiological factors in different diseases and in different mental illnesses varies.

The main psychopathological symptoms in children. It is very common to frighten children with mental disorders, such as telling scary stories before going to bed when they are eating, showing cartoons, which can affect their psyche, making them sleepy and whimpering.

Perception is the reflection in the mind of the surrounding objects and events by direct action on the receptors of the sensory organs. Feeling together with the sensory process provides a person with a

direct emotional purpose in the outside world. Feeling is an important stage of knowledge and thinking, and is always associated to some degree with thinking, memory, and attention. If a person perceives in his mind the individual features of the thing, the event, the events that surround him through intuition, through perception he perceives them as a whole, together with all their features. But based on that, perception is not a sum of perceptions.

At the heart of the cognitive process is the synthesis in the cerebral cortex, which occurs as a result of the simultaneous action of several sensory organs, that is, the temporal connection (conditioned reflex). Perception is usually voluntary or involuntary.

Perception has its own characteristics. These include speed, completeness, accuracy and correctness of perception, but at the same time mental changes depend on changes in the whole organism.

Disorders of perception. Hallucinator images can be very large (macropsy) or very small (micropsy).

Hallucinations are colored or colorless, sometimes monochromatic. False hallucinations make the patient see what is happening, what is happening on stage and on the movie screen.

Hearing hallucinations. These include bells, bells, bullets, and more. Depending on the intensity of the auditory hallucinations, it can be slow, loud, or blurry. They can be heard from above, below, from one side or the other, sometimes from afar, sometimes from close.

Taste and visual hallucinations are also present to some degree, and we see that these qualities are altered or impaired in one way or another in various mental

illnesses. This group includes a set of signs that are characterized by various disorders of perception, feeling, imagination. In many cases, disorders of abstract cognition (thinking, analysis, criticism) are involved in their formation, but the following symptoms play a major role in the violation of the sensory foundations of cognition.

Hyperesthesia is an increase in the perception of moderate external stimuli, which is normal. Normal light dazzles the eye. The surrounding objects (objects) are clearly visible. The sound of the door closing is like a shot being fired, as if the sounds are deafening. The sounds coming from the dishes are unbearably loud. The smells are very pungent. Clothes that touch the skin feel rough. These disorders are manifested in extreme fatigue and the onset of acute psychosis, as well as the development of a state of confusion.

Hypesthesia is the opposite of hyperesthesia. It is characterized by a decrease in the reception of external stimuli. The environment is the same as in the district, with vague objects becoming colorless and indistinct. The sounds become muffled, the surrounding sounds lose their resonance and become indistinguishable. It all seems to freeze motionless.

Psychosensory disorders. Psychosensory disorders include metamorphoses, body structure disorders, depersonalization, and derealization. Psychosensory disturbances or functional hallucinations occur only as a result of external external influences and continue until the end of the effect without adding to it.

Metamorphopsies. Perception of something and a violation of the size or structure of space. In this case, the patient is surrounded by small objects

Illusions. It is a misunderstanding of a real existing object. What is perceived is that illusions differ from hallucinations in the presence of events. Illusions, like hallucinations, are heard through the senses, but the stranger, the stranger, seems to be familiar, as if he had seen them before. In tactile hallucinations, the patient feels the presence of various insects on the skin, the presence of various foreign objects on or under the skin.

Disorders of body structure. In the case of a partial perception of the structure and size of the body, and in the case of a disorder the patient has an impression that the body is enlarged or reduced, heavier or lighter, in the case of a partial disorder the body feels as if some part of the body has changed. The larvae appear to have enlarged or shrunk. Often, body metastases appear to be accompanied by metamorphoses.

Thinking and its disorder. The process of thinking consists of the stages of analysis and synthesis, comparison, comparison, visualization and definition, generalization, and then the transition to the formation of the concept. The material basis of thinking is the word.

Thinking is an important process in the cognitive activity of the individual and is the highest form of reflection of the surrounding being in the human mind. Feeling, imagining, perceiving, is the beginning of the process of knowing. Patients respond more slowly to specific, irrelevant details instead of clear, concise

answers. The physiological basis of thinking is the activity of the cortex of the cerebral hemispheres. Thinking disorders can take the following forms: impaired speed of association, loss of order and purposeful connection between certain ideas, impaired judgment and inference.

Memory impairment. Memory is a reflection of life experience, knowledge and realities in our minds, short and long storage. Humans have motor, or mechanical, and visual, auditory, emotional, and thinking memories. Memory impairment is caused by a decrease in the motor function of the cerebral cortex.

Disorders of consciousness. Consciousness is a high level of reflection of a real being in the brain, which is manifested in a person's ability to know the world around him, the present and the past, to make decisions and to control their behavior depending on the situation. . Consciousness is a very complex unifying activity of the brain, which means to be purposeful and active in time, place, around people and in oneself. Consciousness is the highest form of reflection in the human brain of the real reality that society has created as a result of labor.

The mind is closely connected with all aspects of the mental process. Exercising the brain requires the most comfortable movement of the brain. Any type of change in consciousness is a violation of physiological processes in the brain.

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